

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7656697>

Abstract: education is an integral part of a holistic pedagogical process aimed at the comprehensive (mental, moral, physical) formation of personality. Movement training in physical education is carried out both under the direct supervision of the educator and in the independent activity of children under his supervision. When teaching motor activity, the cognitive, volitional and emotional forces of the child develop, his practical motor skills are formed. Learning by action has a purposeful effect on the inner world of the child from the point of view of his feelings, thinking, gradually forming worldview, moral qualities in the motor activity carried out by children, useful for health and general physical development.

Keywords: education, physical culture, pedagogical skills, healthy lifestyle, health.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБЛАСТИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ И СПОРТА

АННОТАЦИЯ: воспитание является составной частью целостного педагогического процесса, направленного на всестороннее (умственное, нравственное, физическое) формирование личности. Обучение движениям в физическом воспитании осуществляется как под непосредственным руководством воспитателя, так и в самостоятельной деятельности детей под его наблюдением. При обучении двигательной деятельности развиваются познавательные, волевые и эмоциональные силы ребенка, формируются его практические двигательные навыки. Обучение действиям оказывает целенаправленное воздействие на внутренний мир ребенка с точки зрения его чувства, мышления, постепенно формирующегося мировоззрения, нравственных качеств в осуществляемой детьми двигательной деятельности, полезной для здоровья и общефизического развития.

Ключевые слова: воспитание, физическая культура, педагогическое мастерство, здоровый образ жизни, здоровье.

INTRODUCTION

Today, New Uzbekistan is gaining its place in the ranks of the world community. Every industry in the country, especially the education sector, is being developed in a unique and appropriate way to the Times. As a result of the expansion of the content, goals and objectives of education over periods, its forms and methods are also improving. Currently, the main areas of human activity are developing from this activity into a holistic system, that is, technologies that provide the possibility of fulfilling the intended goals. In the same field of Education, pedagogical technology has begun to apply in recent years.

Over the years, the theory and practice of pedagogical technology has been studied unrelated, and it was within the framework of various activities. Today, wide opportunities have been created in our country to consolidate the scientific potential of specialists[1.56]. The fact that a unit of theory and practice is being provided opens the way for determining the true nature of pedagogical technology. In our opinion, pedagogical technology cannot be considered as a separate branch of pedagogical science or as a system aimed only at optimizing educational practice[2, 13].

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Pedagogical technology determines the areas of activity within the framework of combining theoretical and practical research in this area. The essence of the research here is to make modernization based on the study of the elements that make up the pedagogical system. The reason is that the organization of any educational and educational process reflects one or another pedagogical system. Hence, pedagogical technology is a project of a certain pedagogical system that can be introduced into practice.

The main elements of pedagogical technology are as follows:

1. Communication of the educator with educators in the technology of pedagogical communication.
2. Assessment technology, pedagogical assessment and its criteria.
3. Technology of influence of information.
4. The technology of creating and solving pedagogical situations.

Currently, as a result of the development of Science, Technology and innovative technologies, interest in increasing the effectiveness of education is increasing day by day, using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process [2, 57]. The training, in which modern technologies are used in the educational system, is aimed at finding the acquired knowledge by the students themselves, independently studying it and evaluating them, valuing their knowledge, drawing the right conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, acquisition and upbringing of the individual and the team, as well as working and acting in mutual cooperation with free-thinking fellow students, thereby acting in one cell, as a presenter, as a guide. In the educational process, the student becomes a central participant. Currently, as a result of the development of Science, Technology and innovative technologies, interest in increasing the effectiveness of education is increasing day by day, using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process. The training, in which modern technologies are used in the educational system, is aimed at finding the acquired knowledge by the students themselves, independently studying it and evaluating them, valuing their knowledge, drawing the right conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, acquisition and upbringing of the individual and the team, as well as working and acting in mutual cooperation with free-thinking fellow students, thereby acting in one cell, as a presenter, as a guide. In the educational process, the student becomes a central participant.

It is known that physical education and sports activities lead to the comprehensive physical development and strengthening of the human body, improvement and health improvement of physiological functions. Correctly organized physical education classes, taking into account the age, gender and specific characteristics of those involved, will have a high effect [3, 45]. Otherwise they lose the importance of physical education in solving the task of wellness.

Physical education is a pedagogical process, aimed at morphologically and functionally improving the human body, the formation and improvement of the basic skills, skills of movement important for its life, the knowledge associated with them) here in this definition, the specificity of physical education as an independent type of human education leads to the fact that the presence of those noted.

Physical perfection is interpreted differently as a concept that has its own ideal classification for any historical period that changes historically, because this ideal reflects the economic conditions of the population, the worldview of social life. Physically fit is a historically formed

perception of the norm of health and the level of comprehensive physical fitness, which optimally meets the requirements of longevity of labor, public, military and human creative activities.

The recorded elements are manifested in a special way, each depending on the task at hand. Physical education reflects both the laws of physical development and the social laws of physical education. The character and way in which Physical Education uses social laws actually comes from the economic and political system of society.

The perception of students as individuals in the educational process, the use of various pedagogical technologies and modern methods strengthen students' interest in independent, free thinking, research, creative approach to each issue, a sense of responsibility, conducting scientific research, organizing, making the most of scientific literature, most importantly, their interest in reading, science and the profession of their choice, as well as Therefore, it is extremely necessary for professors and teachers operating in educational institutions to know the application of innovative technologies in their place in their classes.

In the process of Physical Education, General pedagogical principles can be applied, since this process is a private phenomenon of education and upbringing. It plays a special role in the field of physical education, reflecting its nature[3, 12].

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The principle of systematicity and consistency solves the issues of studying physical exercises and movements in a form that develops in the same system from simple to complex. The requirements of the physical education program are always met and studied. New training materials the physical exercises studied will be connected and strengthened. On the basis of the program, if simple exercises are first studied, then gradually complex exercises techniques and tactics are formed. When teaching exercises of different levels, exercises are developed from simple to complex. At the same time they are changed during each session.

The principle of strengthening knowledge and skills and skills requires constant repetition, strengthening and development of educational materials. Because, the skills and skills of the exercise are lost if the exercise of physical activity is not repeated. Therefore, when planning training materials, it is necessary to correctly distribute the exercises and reflect on their implementation from simple to complex.

The success of any educational process also depends on how consciously and actively the educators themselves react to this work. The correct understanding of the tasks of the physical education process, their active implementation with interest will speed up the course of Education, allow you to deeply improve the knowledge, skills and skills generated and use them creatively in life. These regularities are primarily the basis of the principle of mindfulness and activism.

CONCLUSION

In addition to the conditions indicated at each stage of physical education, the norm of fulfillment is determined by the expediency of the chosen style, as well as the organization of training in general. Qualifications and skills are a previously formed qualification base. That is why the issue of being able to do will be inextricably linked with other styles of education and upbringing, with the duration of classes and with the styles of regularly increasing difficulties.

One of the decisive conditions for being able to perform in the process of physical education is the duration of physical exercise. Continuity is achieved from natural interactions between different forms of action as well as structurally. This legality is called the transition from a certain to an unknown or from an mastered to an undeveloped task. One of the conditions that is important when moving from one task to another, from easy to difficult, is consistency. The possibilities of

the organism are slow, which means that the requirements should also not be excessive in the possibilities of the organism.

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